

THE ROLE OF MARKETING IN THE MANAGEMENT OF SERVICES IN TOURISM

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Abstract. *Communication with customers is considered with the aim of convincing the consumer that the desired resort and service, attractions and expected interests are fully compatible with the satisfaction of the customer's desire.*

Keywords: *Marketing, service, consumer, tourism, service, product, activity. Demand.*

РОЛЬ МАРКЕТИНГА В МЕНЕДЖМЕНТЕ УСЛУГ В ТУРИЗМЕ

Аннотация. *Общение с клиентами рассматривается с целью убедить потребителя в том, что желаемый курорт и сервис, достопримечательности и ожидаемые интересы полностью совместимы с удовлетворением желания клиента.*

Ключевые слова: *Маркетинг, услуга, потребитель, туризм, услуга, продукт, деятельность. Требование.*

INTRODUCTION

Tourism does not differ from other forms of economic activity in its important features. Therefore, all existing features of modern marketing can be fully applied in tourism.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

At the same time, there is a characteristic of tourism that differs from other forms of trade in services and not only in products. Here, both trade and service take place as products (according to experts, services make up 75% of tourism, products 25%), and tourism service and product consumption are important in their production.

In traditional production with a clear result of work, the concept of marketing has a clear meaning.

RESULTS

The result of activity in tourism is a tourist product. A tourist product is any type of service that satisfies one or another demand of tourists and is paid for by them. The tourist service includes hotel, transport, excursion, translation, household-utility, mediation and other services. At the same time, "tourist product" can be considered in a wide and narrow scope. Tourism in the narrow sense is a product, a service of the tourist industry in a specific direction, that is, a set of standardized services sold to tourists in one "package". Tourist trips sold abroad on the basis of standardized packages or service packages are often called "package tours". These are the main content of the activities of many tourist companies. It should be taken into account that The level of demand for packages varies from country to country. Package tours are mainly used in Belgium, Germany, the Netherlands, Great Britain and Denmark, with a share of 38% of all trips. In Greece, Spain, Italy, the level of demand for packages is low, that is, they do not exceed 30%.

The International Tourism Organization distinguishes three tasks of marketing in tourism:

- ❖ contact with customers;
- ❖ development;
- ❖ control.

Customer communication aims to convince the consumer(s) that the intended vacation destination and the available services, attractions, and expected benefits are fully compatible with the satisfaction of the customer's desires.

Development aims to introduce innovations that can provide new opportunities for sales. In turn, the introduction of such innovations should correspond to the wishes and requirements of potential customers.

Control is the analysis of the results of activities on the penetration of services into the market and the verification of how well these results reflect the full and successful use of the available opportunities in the field of tourism.

First of all, the tourist product should be well received. In this regard, tourism marketing shows the sequence of actions of tourist enterprises aimed at achieving such goals. Therefore, the following definitions of tourism marketing are reasonable and reasonable.

Marketing in tourism means a system of continuous coordination of the offered services with other services. Here, the demand in the market is used, and the tourist enterprise will be able to offer the service more efficiently and profitably compared to other competitors. This long definition embodies a number of ideas, and we will explore these in more detail.

The first idea is as follows: Marketing is not an individual activity, but a system of activities. In other words, it is a sequence of tourism enterprise activities that must be combined to achieve the set goals. At this point, marketing is not only the sale of advertisements and services or the mere development of services, but a system in which all tasks and actions consistent with the marketing concept should be combined.

The above situation means that marketing is different from commercial work (activity). If commercial activity is expressed in the use of all forces and means to accelerate sales, then the purpose of marketing is the process of interaction of developing and selling services in accordance with consumer demand.

The second idea is important, and its purpose is that marketing is not completed in one action. It is not a one-way process, where the timing of applying new prices or attracting new tourist products is considered. The fact is that the market is always in a state of movement and dynamics. For example, consumer demand changes under the influence of various factors, and competitors also work to attract new services to the market. These examples show that marketing is really a continuous process, and the tourism organization should be continuously involved in it. Thus, marketing looks to the future and is not limited to the present.

The third idea is that marketing provides insight into what needs to be done to meet customer demand. Here, the customer is not only thinking about what he is consuming in the current situation, but also what he can buy in other situations (for example, when his income increases). Marketing, as mentioned above, requires foresight. It embodies, in itself, the formation or prediction of the right views that may be necessary for consumers. It also provides an opportunity to evaluate whether it is possible to force people who are not considered clients of the firm to apply for the services offered by them (the firm).

The fourth idea emphasizes that marketing enables the application and identification of profit maximization tools. This makes it only economy level. The goals of the tourist company should be realized in exchange for quality satisfaction of customer demand for a long enough time.

Characteristics of service marketing. Along with product capital and labor markets, there is also a vast service market that operates alongside them. The service sector is a future and rapidly developing sector of the economy. In industrialized countries, the weight of services makes up more than 70% of the gross domestic product. At the same time, the number of people employed in the service sector is increasing. Despite the rapid development of the service sector and its great importance in the economy, the concept of "service" has not yet been given a general definition. F. According to Kotler's definition, "Service is an object of sale as actions, interests, or satisfactions." It follows from this definition that

Various services are in circulation in the service market. For this reason, the service market is divided into narrow structural markets. Services usually include: transport, communication, trade, material and technical support, household and communal services, banking and finance, science, education, health care, culture and art, physical education, sports, tourism, etc.

In the provision of services, the common side of various labor activities is created - consumption value that does not have a material form. Therefore, the service market is fundamentally different from other markets. There are two main reasons for this difference.

First, the service does not exist until it is fulfilled, that is, the product is created in the process of providing the service. This situation does not make it possible to compare two different service providers, two competing firms, their services, even if their products appear to be the same. The quality of service can be compared after implementation. We have the opportunity to compare material goods before buying them. We only have the opportunity to compare the condition of the expected and after the service.

Second, the service industry requires special knowledge and skills that are difficult for the customer to not only appreciate, but even to understand. Abstraction in the process of service can put the customer in an uncomfortable situation, as well as hurt, anger, cause distrust. Therefore, in this field, the buyer always wants to work with a certain service provider. This situation is more profitable for the service provider, which creates a factor of repetition of such communications.

The above aspects apply to all service markets. In general, the uniqueness of the service requires a special approach to business activities to meet the demand for the service. In addition to the variety of services, they have in common, they are of four types:

- ❖ Intangibility.
- ❖ Continuity of production and consumption.
- ❖ Quality variability.
- ❖ Inability to save.

Intangibility means that the service is not tangible, it cannot be demonstrated, tried, studied before receiving it. It is very difficult to evaluate and discuss what is sold to the customer, sometimes after and before receiving the service. Therefore, he has to believe the words of the service provider. As a result, the consumer will definitely have elements of hope and trust in the service provider.

At the same time, the intangible nature of the service makes it difficult for the seller. At least two problems arise in the service business. On the one hand, it is very difficult to show customers your product, on the other hand, it is even more difficult to explain to them what they are paying for. Only after the service has been provided to the customer can the salesperson

highlight its benefits, but the service can only be evaluated after it has been performed. In addition, there are types of services that customers cannot evaluate even after they have been performed (for example, in medicine). It can be said that the concept of service in marketing is profit, income. Continuity of production and service consumption is one of the important features. Service can be performed only when the customer appears or the order is received. From this point of view, some experts believe that the continuity of production and consumption shows exactly that factor, that is, their difference from the material form of products.

The continuity of the relationship between production and consumption, many types of services are considered to be inseparable, regardless of who offers them. Therefore, personal service in a hotel cannot be separated from a hotel attendant, restaurant service from a waiter, ticket sales service from a cashier.

Figure 1 shows the difference between a service and a product in terms of the relationship between production and consumption.

Drawing 1.

Involving the customer in the service consumption and production process means that the marketer should be concerned not only with what to produce, but also with how to produce it. The main meaning is occupied by the second issue. Therefore, the correct selection and training of persons who enter into contracts with customers is necessary to ensure the quality of service and to create the confidence of the buyer in this or that firm. In addition, the buyer often monitors the service of the seller as a kind of expert, whose knowledge and professional skills he relies on. In this sense, the seller's service will always be a part of it.

The inevitable result of the continuity of production and consumption is the variability of service quality. The quality of service depends on who, where and when it is provided. For example, the quality of service in one hotel is high, and in another it is low. One of the hotel staff is polite and friendly, and the other is rude and rude. Even the same good employee performs different services during the workday.

Two groups of factors have a major impact on service variability. The first group is directly related to working with individuals in the enterprise. Therefore, the variability of the service quality may be related to the lack of high qualification of workers, slowness of their training, lack of information and handling aspects, lack of appropriate control over the performance of individuals. Second, the important basis of service variability is related to the

high level of individuality of the service in accordance with the customer's requirements, that is, its rarity. At the same time, it requires a systematic, comprehensive and thorough study of consumer behavior. As a result, it provides an opportunity to learn the psychological aspects of managing consumer demand or working with customers in a service company. Standardized service delivery is developed to reduce service variability. The service standard is a (complex) comprehensive obligation to fulfill the customer's service rules, which calls for guaranteeing the specified quality level of all developed operations.

DISCUSSION

So, the American Airlines service standard will be as follows:

- order calls must be answered after 20 seconds;
- 85% of passengers should not stand in line for more than 5 minutes;
- flight time may change by no more than 5 minutes from the schedule;
- doors must be opened 70 seconds after landing;
- there is always a stock of necessary magazines in the salon.

Diligent adherence to regulations makes it one of the preferred firms by passengers. The main feature of the service is its inability to maintain. The Service cannot be reserved for future sale. If demand exceeds supply, such as when a store takes a product out of stock, the situation cannot be changed. On the other hand, if the service capacity exceeds the demand for them, it will result in a loss of profit. The lack of maintenance means that special measures must be taken to balance supply and demand. This line can include:

- ❖ setting differentiated prices;
- ❖ applying discounts;
- ❖ introducing a system of advance orders;
- ❖ increase the speed of service;
- ❖ combining the functions of individuals.

On the basis of marketing research, periods of decrease and increase in demand are determined by foreign airlines; the increase was observed from June 15 to September 30 and on weekends, and the decrease was observed in other periods. This helped to develop a system of incentives for travel during periods of reduced demand.

The cheapest prices for tickets are set during the period of decline. On New Year's holidays, they are increased by an average of 10%. Midweek tickets are cheaper than weekends. "Sunday rule" applies from weekends to change the demand. Accordingly, passengers will be able to use the preferential return ticket next Monday. In other cases, they must pay the full price.

The considered characteristics of service provision (intangibility, production and consumption continuity, quality variability, inability to store) increase the risk of purchase and make it difficult to evaluate. Research on risk appetite in the service industry compares consumers' perceptions of perceived risk and service variability to the purchase of tangible products. The service provider should pay attention to such risks and take measures to reduce them. This will help not only to increase regular customers, but also to attract additional buyers.

Thus, the nature of the service market, the nature of the service and the nature of its acceptance by consumers, means the nature of marketing in the field. The main task of service marketing is to help customers evaluate the company and its service.

At the level of individual economic entities, marketing is an integrated system of

planning product assortment, volume, distribution over selected markets, sales and pricing, ensuring the achievement of a variety of benefits that leads to the satisfaction of both producers and consumers. This definition is broad enough to include the activities of non-profit organizations. Thus, marketing is the activity of a tourist enterprise for customers. For commercial organizations, the main purpose of which is to make a profit, when marketing is narrowly defined in the entrepreneurial sense, it is understood as a management system of production and sales activities aimed at obtaining the necessary profit by taking into account the market conditions of the organization and actively influencing them.

CONCLUSIONS

It follows from this that the large number of fields of use of marketing leads to a wide variety of definitions given to marketing.

Tourism marketing is a set of methods and methods of organizing the promotion of tourist services and attracting attention. Tourism marketing contacts with existing and prospective customers; development of the tourism sector (construction, design of new tours); should control the satisfaction of touristic demand.

REFERENCES

1. On measures related to the rapid development of the tourism network" Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 5, 2019 No. PQ-4095.
2. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4755 dated June 19, 2020 "On additional measures to develop the tourism sector in strict compliance with the requirements of the enhanced sanitary and epidemiological safety regime".
3. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-5249 dated September 22, 2021 "On financial support for activities to be implemented in order to further accelerate large-scale construction and beautification works in Samarkand region and increase tourism potential."
4. "On measures to further improve the continuous system of training qualified personnel in the fields of tourism, cultural heritage and museology" Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 30, 2021 No. PQ-5270.
5. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4861 of December 2, 2016 "On measures to ensure rapid development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
6. Decree No. PF-5033 dated May 4, 2017 "On amendments and additions to some decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
7. Abdurahmanov K.Kh. Management tourism: uchebnoe posobie. - T.: Branch FGBOU VPO "REU im. G.V. Plekhanova" v g. Tashkent, 2013. – 248 p.
8. Azar V.I., Tumanov S.Yu. Ekonomika turistskogo rinka. - M.: IPKT, 1998. - 239 p.
9. Aleksandrova A.Yu. International tourism. - M.: Aspekt press, 2016. - 470 p.
10. Alimov R., Kamilova M., Kurbanova D. Cluster concept of economic development: theory and practice. - T.: Institut ekonomiki AN Ruz., 2005. - S. 36.
11. Alieva M.T., Umurjanov A. Economy of tourist countries. - T.: Economy - Finance, 2005. - 339 p.
12. Babkin A.V. Special tourism. - Rostov-on-Don: Phoenix, 2008. - 252 p.

13. Balabanov I.T., Balabanov A.I. Economic tourism. Uchebnoe posobie. - M.: Finance and statistics, 2003. - 176 p.
14. Balabanov I.T. Economic tourism / I.T. Balabanov, A.I. Balabanov - M.: Finance and statistics, 2002. – S. 25.
15. Birzhakov M.B. Introduction to tourism. – Izdanie 9-e pererabotannoe i dopolnennoe. - SPb.: Izdatelsky dom Gerda, 2007. - 576 p.
16. MS Azimovna Improving The Study Of Consumer Behavior *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 109-112
17. MS Azimovna Stages of the Econometric Research and Modeling Process
18. Central Asian Journal of Innovations on Tourism Management and Finance 3
19. MS Azimovna Scientific-Methodical Issues of Evaluation of Marketing Service in Hotels *Central Asian Journal of Innovations on Tourism Management and Finance* 3
20. MS Azimovna Efficiency of advertising activities of trading organizations and ways to increase IT *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities* 12 (3), 93-97
21. Azimovna MS, Ilkhomovna UD Problems of Marketing in the System of Higher Education // *Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability.* - 2022. - T. 13. – S. 71-75.
22. Azimovna MS, Ilkhomovna UD, Shokhrukhovich UF INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN // *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION.* - 2022. - T. 2. – no. 1. – S. 1-4.
23. Musayeva SA, Usmonova DI, Usmanov FS Problems with Marketing Research in the Furniture Market // *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research.* - 2021.
24. Azimovna MS, Shokhrukhovich UF Development Prospects of Business Subjects in the Republic of Uzbekistan // *Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal.* - 2022. - T. 1. – no. 4. – S. 13-19.
25. Azimovna MS, Ilkhomovna UD, Shokhrukhovich UF The Concept of Marketing Policy in Trade and Service Enterprises // *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS ON TOURISM MANAGEMENT AND FINANCE.* - 2022. - T. 3. – no. 8. - S. 1-5. *SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 1 ISSUE 5* UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337 105
26. Azimovna MS, Shokhrukhovich UF Ways to expand network marketing and e-commerce in the wholesale of medicines // *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES* ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876. - 2022. - T. 16. – no. 06. – S. 113-116.
27. Azimovna MS, Shokhrukhovich US THE ROLE OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS IN THE FOREIGN TRADE TURNOVER OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN // *SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF SUSTAINABILITY AND LEADING RESEARCH ONLINE.* - 2022. - T. 2. – no. 6. - S. 110-112.
28. Azimovna MS IMPROVING THE STUDY OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOR // *Gospodarka i Innowacje.* - 2022. - S. 109-112.
29. Azimovna MS et al. Analysis of the main economic and marketing indicators of FE" DAKA-TEX" LLC // *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW* ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. - 2022. - T. 11. – no. 06. – S. 4-7.
30. Azimovna MS, Ilkhomovna UD Optimal principles of assessing the quality of graduates in higher education // *Eurasian Scientific Herald.* - 2022. - T. 8. - S. 233-238.

31. Azimovna MS THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF THE MARKETING COMPLEX TO INCREASE THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF PRODUCTS //FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES. - 2022. - T. 1. – no. 9. - S. 20-23.
32. Usmanov Ilkhom Achilovich, The role of innovative processes and investments in increasing the efficiency of construction services. Science and Innovation. International scientific journal. Volume 1 Issue 5 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337 – p/ 37
33. Usmanov Ilkhom Achilovich. Research of marketing activities of S Sharq-Universal-SMK LLC. Science and Innovation. International Scientific Journal. Volume 1 Issue 5 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337 – p. 13